

FERTILITY BEHAVIOUR AND FAMILY SIZE PREFERENCE OF WOMEN WITH CHRONIC INFECTION: ANALYSIS OF ABA WOMEN

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ABSTRACT

Women's fertility suffers a setback when a woman is infected. The fallopian tubes and ovaries are affected by childbearing and affect the capacity for family size determination. This paper analysed secondary data on the fertility behaviour and family size preference of women with chronic infection. Analysed data revealed especially in third world countries such as those found in Africa, chronic infection through diseases like HIV/AIDS, malaria and tuberculosis continue to disrupt women's fertility life and hence their childbearing preference. The researchers opined the need for the government to pay attention to the health being of women as a measure of maintaining the population progression of the world.

KEYWORDS: Women's Fertility, Fertility Behaviour, Chronic Infection, and Family Size Preference

INTRODUCTION

Fertility preferences are important for population studies, management, development and planning programmers in societies. The ideal family size, which has to do with the number of children wanted in one's lifetime, is one of the variables used in measuring fertility preferences among families (WHO 2019). However, this varies among families with facilities like higher academic attachment compared to those with lower qualifications. Demographers have studied the trends and predictors of population growth as well as preferences of family size among economically variable and educated families.

There has been comparatively less research into the determinants of individual-level preference of family size, and although family size preferences are powerfully shaped by societal norms and social status (Ryder 1976/2010) of families, the practice considerably varies among communities. Importantly, individuals themselves in their reproductive lives are influenced by their economic status and level of education. However, individual-level preferences also evolve through the influence of religious affiliation, economy and literacy level. The determinants of family size preferences assume that the fertility behaviour of women is determined principally by their level of awareness which enhances their fertility

level and family size (Bankolly 1995). However as one's life circumstances unfold in often unanticipated ways, studies indicate that relationships between individuals' family size preferences and sociodemographic characteristics, attitudes, and values play a vital role in determining the preference state of couples on the number of children (Bankole 1995; Ezeh *et al.*, 1996; Hayford and Morgan 2008; McCarthy and Oni 1987). The largely cross-sectional nature of most studies stands in contrast to the potentially dynamic quality of preferences and although men and women may develop family size preferences at young ages, these desires are mutable by social factors over time after marriage. Indeed, as early as the 1960s, studies documented significant changes in family size preferences and expectations over time (Freedman *et al.*, 1965). Also, studies have investigated how individuals' fertility preferences change over time and that the predictors of change in low-fertility contexts are affected by the social reality of the society (e.g., Hayford 2009; Heiland *et al.* 2008; Iacovou and Tavares 2011; Liebroer 2009).

AN OVERVIEW OF FERTILITY BEHAVIOUR

According to the International Encyclopedia of The Social and Behavioral Sciences, 2001, fertility behaviour refers to the childbearing patterns of women or couples, including especially the number of births, the timing of births, and associated reproductive behaviour such as union formation (including marriage and co-habitation) and contraceptive behaviour. The fertility preferences of women refer to women's desired family size and intention to limit or delay childbearing (Sarnak *et al.*, 2021) and ideal family size as well as the number of children wanted in one's lifetime, is one of the variables used to measure fertility preferences or for estimating the level of wanted and unwanted fertility (Thompson, 2015). Although fertility has been declining in developed countries (Skakkebaek *et al.*, 2022) evidence shows that the desired family size is relatively high in sub-Saharan Africa (Atake and Gnakou Ali, 2019; Matovu *et al.*, 2017) giving rise to high population growth and effects on social services (Udom S.D, 2016). This high fertility has serious negative impacts on the health of children and their mothers, child education, human capital investment, economic growth, environment and other social services (Pinter *et al.*, 2016; World Bank, 2010; Forson, Arthur and Ayeh- Kumi, 2018; Blaabaek, Jaeger and Molitoris, 2020).

Economic theories of childbearing relate decisions about family size and the timing of births with the constraints of incomes and prices (Ermisch, 2001). In low- and middle-income countries, decisions about a woman's fertility are influenced by several factors women empowerment, partner influences, social norms and cultural context (Haque *et al.* 2021). On the other hand, it is argued that the perceived ideal number of children is associated with one place of residence, religion, employment deviation and experience of child death (Akarm *et al.*, 2020)

Understanding women's fertility preferences is important for monitoring population growth and developing policies and programs like fertility planning (FP) (DHS program, 2007), as well provide social services (Udom, 2016) to checkmate the excesses of the

population growth. This study was done to assess the decision on ideal family size and its associated factors among women of reproductive age in Aba North Abia state Nyrna.

FERTILITY STOPPING BEHAVIOUR

Fertility-stopping behaviour refers to fertility control. According to Henry (1961); control depends on the number of children already born (parity) and increases when the couple achieves the desired family size while spacing behaviour refers to deliberate fertility control that is independent of parity

FAMILY SIZE PREFERENCE

Family size preference could also be seen as Desired Family Size, which is the number of children wanted in one's lifetime and is viewed as a measure of the demand for children which, in combination with the supply of children and contraception determines the number of children born.

DETERMINANTS OF FAMILY SIZE PREFERENCE

A good number of factors have been documented as the determinant of family size by couples. It is preferred by women. These are the ages of the spouse at marriage family income, educational status, number of living children, number of desired children, sex preferences, contraceptive use, family planning and residence, other factors include; the socio-cultural factors and chronic infections which affect women. The sociocultural factors may include couples' religion and belief system.

CHRONIC INFECTIONS AMONG WOMEN IN ABA NORTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ABIA STATE

HIV/AIDS

In addition to hunger, lack/poor attendant of education, and environmental and sociocultural constraints, STDs like HIV/AIDS and malaria, along with tuberculosis, continue to disproportionately affect and further weaken the condition of women in many of the world's poorest regions. Recent estimates indicate that more than half of the estimated (WHO, 2021) 38 million cases of adult HIV infection worldwide are women. Moreover, the social, economic, and psychological effects of the disease are more severe for women than their partners. In sub-Saharan Africa records the highest cases of HIV infection (WHO, 2021). The largest gender difference occurs among younger age groups and in Aba. HIV infections among women are also on the rise. Analysis of newly diagnosed HIV infections that occurred between 1999 and 2022 showed that more than two-thirds of victims (64%) are women.

HIV infection in women has obvious implications for the health and well-being of children. Since it can be transmitted perinatally, increasing numbers of children- estimated

at 12 million- are said to have been orphaned by the disease (Udara, 2006). Although preventing HIV transmission from an infected mother to her infant has become feasible due to effective antiretroviral treatment regimens and has met with great success in many parts of the world, services that prevent mother-to-child transmission are severely limited in low-income societies and industrial/busy areas like Aba. Similarly, although a combination of antiretroviral therapy offers the potential to manage the disease as a chronic, treatable condition, access to such treatment is primarily limited to persons in high-income countries, which excludes the most severely affected regions. As an example, 4.1 million persons in Africa need such therapy, but <2% have access to the drugs.

Preventing new infections is fundamental to stopping fertility imbalance among women. Attaining this goal requires that all persons have information about the disease and know their infection status. This is, thus a formidable challenge in both low- and high-income countries. Such information can help uninfected persons remain free of the disease and help those who are infected gain access to treatment and prevent transmission to their partners. Fortunately, several broad-based national and international initiatives have been taken towards meeting these challenges. For example, the President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief is a 5-year, \$15 billion to help treat infection prevent new infections among pregnant women and reduce mortality. Other undertakings include the United Nations' Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis, and Malaria and "The 3 by 5 Initiative," a detailed, multicountry plan developed by the World Health Organization and the Joint United Nations Programme to provide antiretroviral treatment to 3 million HIV-infected persons in developing countries by the end of 2025.

MALARIA IN WOMEN

Malaria is another infectious disease threat that disproportionately affects women; it causes serious illness in pregnant women and children <5 years of age. Every year, malaria kills 1.5 million to 2.7 million persons and adversely affects another 300,000 to 500,000, (Udom, S.D 2016). In Africa, pregnant women suffer decreased immunity to malaria, which affects their chances of having healthy children and they have an increased risk for severe maternal anemia. The consequent impaired fetal growth contributes to low birth weight in newborns. Malaria during pregnancy causes as many as 10,000 maternal deaths each year 8%-14% of all low birth weight babies, and 3%-8% of all infant deaths in third world countries.

OTHER INFECTIOUS DISEASES IN WOMEN

In addition to HIV, women are more susceptible to other Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs) and their long-term complications affect their childbearing patterns. In the United States >50% of preventable infertility is related to STDs and in addition, most sexually transmitted pathogens can be passed to the fetus or infant, sometimes with fatal consequences. (World Health Organization 2019). Longitudinal studies show that women

are also at greater risk for active disease from *mycobacterium tuberculosis* infection and Case-fatality rates are likewise higher in women fetuses. WHO (2019) revealed that reasons behind this include decreased immune function due to poor nutritional status and delays in seeking care, both of which can be a function of gender, income and literacy

The tropical parasitic disease schistosomiasis presents special concerns for women. Among parasitic diseases, schistosomiasis is second to malaria in prevalence; as it affects >200 million persons in 74 countries. In affected areas, women are at greater risk for the disease compared to men because of their increased exposure to contaminated water through domestic work such as washing clothes and preparing food. The consequences of the disease are more severe in women than in men. Female genital schistosomiasis, often misdiagnosed as an STD, can cause tumours, ulcers, and infertility and may increase the risk for STDs (WHO, 2019). Because of these infections and the chances of the infected women losing their lives during delivery, the family size preference behaviours become sizable and shaped by the experiences of or women. Especially where they can't have access to orthodox prescribed drugs (Wilson, *et al.*, 2020; Peters *et al.*, 2020).

FAMILY SIZE PREFERENCES, INTENTIONS, AND BIRTHS

The relationship between family size desires and births depends on the relationships between preferences and intentions that influence the behaviour of the couples towards childbirth. Couples' child planning and disagreement are a primary source of gaps between the desires and intentions of couples. that is, the gap between individual desires and intentions to have a child is explained in large part by a spouse's different preferences (Thomson 1997). Another key source of gaps between desires and intentions is the perception of control over fertility. Those who believe themselves to be infecund may desire more children than they intend; and also those who do not perceive themselves to be able to control fertility may give birth to more children than they may have desired or intend.

Family size preferences or intentions may also change over the life course and are particularly likely to be influenced by experiences with previous births (Namboodiri 1983). Despite these expected gaps, measures of family size desires, particularly the desire for additional children, have moderately strong effects on fertility behaviour and outcomes of parents (McClelland 1983). Lee (1980) has demonstrated that a 'moving target' model of desired and achieved fertility produces even stronger correspondence between family size desires and period of fertility. Davidson and Jaccard (1979) identified many of the key conditions under which a strong effect of fertility desires or intentions on births should be expected. First, the strength of the effect depends on the extent to which the ultimate goal (birth or no birth) is achieved through a sequence of behaviours and events, including sexual intercourse, contraception, conception, and abortion. Fertility desires and intentions should have stronger effects on the behaviours of couples at the beginning of the sequence than on the outcome. Second, the effect will be stronger over shorter versus longer periods because

the opportunity for new experiences that change desires or intentions is reduced. Third, the effects of desires or intentions on behaviour and outcomes should be stronger for individuals who place a high value on cognitive consistency that is those who believe they have control over their actions, and who generally engage in planful behaviour than for those who do not. Finally, desires intentions and behaviours as well as their outcomes should be measured at the same level of specificity to expect a strong relationship; desired or ideal family size should not, for example, be expected to have a strong effect on contraceptive use or even the timing of a particular birth. Thus relationship between childbearing desires or intentions and births depends to a considerable extent on the couple's agreement. Couples disagreement leads to birth rates between those of couples who both desire or intend a child and those who do not. This means that both partners desire to have at least some influence on births (Thomson 1997; Thomson and Hoem 1998; Dodoo 1998).

POPULATION POLICIES AND LARGE FAMILY SIZE PREFERENCE

The idea that couples should limit their family size went against cultural mores in many societies, and some governments were loathe to support a potentially unpopular policy. Many governments embraced the more acceptable idea that fertility would decrease and that population growth would slow as living standards increased through economic development. (Udom S, 2016). The above view was expressed at the 1974 UN World Population Conference when an Indian delegate declared that “development is the best contraceptive”. Against this, during the late 1970s and 1980s, concern about the negative effects of population growth on economic development broadened and increasing numbers of countries accepted the idea that government actions could slow population growth. For example in Nigeria, the Babangida administration directs that to meet the economic demand, the family should not have more than one children

National efforts to influence population growth include incentives to have more or fewer children and disincentives for having more than a given number of children. These efforts have met with mixed success and obstacles from religious groups and cultures. Some argue that China's population policies initiated in the 1970s were a success from a demographic perspective. China's TFR decreased from approximately 6.0 in the 1960s to less than 2.0 in the 1990s, in part because of government policies and programs. However, China's stringent “one-child family” policy introduced in 1979 was widely criticized for violating human rights. Between 1975 and 1977, Gandhi's government in India promoted male sterilization campaigns that sometimes led to coercion and public outrage about the reported abuses contributed to the downfall of Gandhi's government creating a backlash against family planning programs in India that took years to overcome.

Women's rights activists and others have generally opposed a demographic rationale for family planning as an infringement on individual rights. They have argued that

women's rights and well-being should take precedence over national interest, while many have criticized the family planning programs' lack of integration with other health services as having detrimental effects on women's health and emotions, thus decisions on child preference should be an issue of choice and not compulsion in the form of government policies.

INFECTIONS IN WOMEN AGAINST FERTILITY/LARGE FAMILY SIZE PREFERENCE

Pelvic infections are an important cause of infertility, primarily as a result of tubal damage, which damages the fallopian tubes. This infection may be due to adhesions, tubal mucosal damage, or tubal occlusion that interferes with normal ovum transport. Sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) can directly or indirectly cause infertility in women. When STDs are left untreated, infections can develop which may cause infertility by moving up the reproductive system and spreading to the woman's uterus, ovaries and fallopian tubes causing damage, scarring or inflaming, and this is most often caused by the STDs like gonorrhoea or chlamydia and when bacteria enter the reproductive system STD causes scarring of the cervix, vagina, ovaries, fallopian tubes and uterus which if left untreated, STD can cause irreversible damage resulting in infertility.

Problems with the fallopian tubes are a leading cause of female infertility and this is caused by STDs which is one of the causes of what is called tubal factor infertility. The American Society for Reproductive Medicine (ASRM) reports that 25%-35% of female infertility is due to tubal factors. If the fallopian tubes are damaged or blocked, this can result in infertility in two ways: it can prevent sperm from reaching the egg in the fallopian tube for fertilization, and it can prevent a fertilized egg from entering the uterus to implant for pregnancy.

Herpes Simplex Virus (HSV), Human Papillomavirus (HPV) and Syphilis can indirectly affect fertility. HSV can cause the couple to abstain from sexual intercourse, which limits the chances of becoming pregnant and this can also cause genital warts that may take months or years to treat. Also, some strains of HPV can lead to cervical cancer or precancerous cells, the treatment of which can affect fertility. Syphilis should be noted if left untreated can affect infertility in women. Gonorrhoea can be contracted by anyone sexually active. Transmitted through vaginal, anal or oral sex, the prevalence of gonorrhoea in young adults ages 15-24 is common because they are more sexually active. Without treatment, gonorrhoea can lead to very serious complications in women and their newborn babies. Gonorrhoea can thrive in a female's reproductive tract, specifically in the uterus and the fallopian tubes causing tubal factor infertility.

CONCLUSION

Family size desires may represent family size preferences. Intentions, expectations, and ideals. Desired family size is the number of children wanted in one's lifetime and is

viewed as a measure of the demand for children which, in combination with the supply of children and contraception determines the number of children born. Family size desires are conceptually and empirically distinct from family size intentions, expectations, and ideals and they vary depending on family status and culture. Desires, intentions, and expectations are often uncertain and change over the life course in response to new experiences, expectations and conditions. Ideas are shaped by the larger society and therefore change more slowly. Because childbearing is a two-person event, the desires and intentions of sexual partners must be considered. As predictors of aggregate or individual fertility, family size desires must be adjusted to take into account partners' desires social changes cultural influence as well as fecundity, fertility control, and other constraints on individual behaviour or outcomes. Following the population policies, infections among women and family planning, family size preference can be reduced to small size.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are made for proper decision as regards women's fertility behaviour and family size preferences.

1. Low fertility should be considered as a working tool for the decrease in population
2. Families should consider low family size preferences to fight population increase. Churches are religious organizations that partner in creating awareness of moderate family size.
3. Personal hygiene should be practised at all times amongst women to avoid infections also, Government, NGOs and CBOs to assist in health awareness at the community level
4. This requires creating more awareness and sensitizing partners on their fertility behaviour, it treatment of infections should be considered important to avert its dangers on reproduction and family size preferences

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